

Robust Wideband Beamforming

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Abstract—Robust wideband beamforming with a real-time array testbed will be studied in this paper. For the practical consideration of uncertainty, channel impulse responses or channel transform functions of RF chains can not be obtained exactly due to the limitation of sounding and calibration procedure. Thus robust optimization will be applied to wideband beamforming. It is assumed that the uncertainty will be bounded and the worst case performance can be guaranteed by robust optimization. Finally, the optimal coefficients for a 2-dimensional filter bank to perform wideband beamforming will be obtained.

Index Terms—wideband beamforming, robust optimization, SDP, steering vector, filter bank.

I. INTRODUCTION

Beamforming is a special case of waveform diversity. Generally speaking, beamforming is a signal processing technique for directional signal transmission and reception in the multi-antenna system or the array system. Beamforming has been studied for several decades and deployed in civil and military systems. Wideband Code Division Multiple Access (WCDMA) supports direction of arrival (DOA) based beamforming and transmit antenna array (TxAA) beamforming. In Long Term Evolution (LTE), multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) precoding based beamforming with Space-Division Multiple Access (SDMA) is used. For phased array radar, narrowband beamforming is widely used to compensate for the phase shifts so that coherent signal combination can be performed. The simplest way to perform narrowband beamforming is based on maximal-ratio combining and the Cauchy Schwarz inequality. Channel state information (CSI) should be known for near field beamforming, and the steering vector is needed for far field beamforming.

However, the traditional narrowband beamforming for phased array radar is not suitable for some applications in tough situations. To counter increasingly complex threats under dynamic radio environment, phased array radar is required to cover multi-GHz frequency band with wide instantaneous bandwidth, e.g. 500 MHz. Phased array radar working with wide frequency band can operate in both spatial domain and frequency domain simultaneously, which greatly improves the radar performance for detection, identification, tracking and surveillance. Robust wideband beamforming with a real-time array testbed will be studied in this paper. The motivation is based on the observation that channel impulse responses or channel transform functions of RF chains can not be obtained

exactly due to the limitation of sounding and calibration procedure. The uncertainty in the system will decrease the performance.

Optimization, or mathematical programming, refers to minimizing or maximizing the objective function by systematically choosing the values of optimization variables from within an allowed set defined by the constraint functions. The optimization issue with uncertainty is becoming hotter and hotter in many research fields, such as operation research, finance, industrial management, transportation scheduling, wireless communication, smart grid and so on, because most of the optimization issues are from dynamic complex system and most of the variables in the optimization issue can not be deterministic or known for sure. There are two approaches to deal with the optimization issue with uncertainty. One is robust optimization and the other is stochastic optimization. In robust optimization, the uncertainty model is deterministic and set-based [1]. However in stochastic optimization, the uncertainty model is assumed to be random [1]. Robust optimization, which is a conservative approach [2], can guarantee the performance for all the cases within the set-based uncertainty. In other words, robustness means the performance is stable with the bounded errors. However, stochastic optimization can only guarantee the performance on average for the uncertainty with known or partially known probability distribution [2] information. Thus there is a tradeoff between robustness and performance.

Robust optimization will be applied to wideband beamforming. It is assumed that the uncertainty from channel transfer functions of RF chains will be bounded. The worst case performance can be guaranteed through robust optimization. A time domain approach for wideband beamforming will be adopted [3] [4]. Tapped delay line structure is exploited and a 2-dimensional filter bank is designed to form the wideband beam pattern. Thus, the core task of wideband beamforming is to obtain optimal coefficients for the 2-dimensional filter bank such that the array response aims at (1) desired main lobe shape with consideration of magnitude and phase; (2) overall constrained side lobes; (3) nulling at given angles and frequency points; (4) frequency invariant property for the given angle range and frequency range.

Robust wideband beamforming will be formulated as semidefinite programming (SDP). SDP-based signal processing is becoming more and more popular recently. It can be

applied to control theory, statistics, circuit design, graph theory and so on. The reasons for this are (1) more and more practical problems can be formulated as SDP; (2) most interior-point methods for linear programming have been generalized to SDP; (3) nowadays the computational capability is increased greatly and SDP can be solved fast. In this way, wideband beamforming can be designed flexibly and adaptively. Multiple spatial beams can be formed to detect or track the threats while multiple spatial nulls can be generated to deny the interferences. Some opaque frequency bands can also be formed to reject harmful interference frequency bands. At the same time, frequency invariant property can be applied in any spatial frequency region based on the performance requirement of phased array radar. Meanwhile, the uncertainty of system will be taken into account in the context of SDP, which will make the wideband beam pattern more stable [5].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In section II the issue on wideband beamforming is presented. Section III will show robust wideband beamforming. Performance of robust wideband beamforming will be provided in section IV, followed by some remarks given in section V.

II. WIDEBAND BEAMFORMING

There are M antennas in the linear array. The distance between antennas is d . The mutual coupling among antennas is not considered in this paper. The system works with the central frequency of f_c and the bandwidth of B . Assume $\delta(t)$ is the signal in the far field of the system and impinges on it from the angle θ . The sampling rate of analog-to-digital converter (ADC) is $1/T_s$ and $1/T_s \geq 2B$,

The equivalent baseband complex responses of RF chains after ADC are measured simultaneously and represented as $h_{m,\theta}$ [k]. By discrete Fourier transform, the discrete channel transfer function $h_{m,\theta,f}$ can be obtained from $h_{m,\theta}$ [k].

Assume angles of arrival of interest are in the set $\Omega_\theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{L+1}\}$ and the frequency points of interest are in the set $\Omega_f = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_{J+1}\}$ such that $f_{J+1} - f_1 \approx B$. After a 2-dimensional filter bank, the array response is defined as $B(f_j, \theta_l)$, which can be expressed as,

$$B(f_j, \theta_l) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} w_{m,n} h_{m,\theta_l, f_j} \exp\{-\sqrt{-1}n2\pi f_j T_s\} \quad (1)$$

where $w_{m,n}$ is the coefficient at the $(n+1)$ -th tap of the $(m+1)$ -th filter.

The array response can be reformulated as the vector representation,

$$B(f_j, \theta_l) = \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the coefficient vector defined as,

$$\mathbf{w} = [\mathbf{w}_0^H \ \mathbf{w}_1^H \ \dots \ \mathbf{w}_{M-1}^H]^H \quad (3)$$

and

$$\mathbf{w}_m = [w_{m,0} \ w_{m,1} \ \dots \ w_{m,N-1}]^H \quad (4)$$

where $(\bullet)^H$ denotes transpose conjugate operation.

$\mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l)$ is the $M \times N$ steering vector. Define $1 \leq i \leq M \times N$,

$$m = \left\lfloor \frac{i-1}{N} \right\rfloor \quad (5)$$

and

$$n = i - m \times N - 1 \quad (6)$$

Each entry in $\mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l)$ is

$$(\mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l))_{1,i} = h_{m,\theta_l, f_j} \exp\{-\sqrt{-1}n2\pi f_j T_s\} \quad (7)$$

The general formulation of optimization issue for wideband beamforming with the consideration of 4 mentioned tasks are presented as follows. If the look direction is at the angle θ_{l_0} , the desired main beam pattern at this angle is $P(f_j, \theta_{l_0})$, the optimization objective is to minimize the Euclidean distance between $P(f_j, \theta_{l_0})$ and $B(f_j, \theta_{l_0})$,

$$\text{minimize} \sum_{f_j \in \Omega_f} |P(f_j, \theta_{l_0}) - B(f_j, \theta_{l_0})|^2 \quad (8)$$

For each frequency point, we would like to constrain array response for side lobe, which can be expressed as,

$$\sum_{\substack{\theta_l \in \Omega_\theta - \theta_{l_0} \\ f_j \in \Omega_f}} |B(f_j, \theta_l)| \leq \varepsilon_{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j) \quad (9)$$

where $\varepsilon_{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j)$ is the side lobe threshold for each frequency point f_j .

If there are nullings at frequency points in the set $\Omega_{f_{\text{nulling}}}$ and angles in the set $\Omega_{\theta_{\text{nulling}}}$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} |B(f_j, \theta_l)| &\leq \varepsilon_{\text{nulling}}(f_j, \theta_l) \\ f_j &\in \Omega_{f_{\text{nulling}}} \\ \theta_l &\in \Omega_{\theta_{\text{nulling}}} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $\varepsilon_{\text{nulling}}(f_j, \theta_l)$ is the nulling threshold for the frequency f_j and the angle θ_l .

Assume the frequency invariant property is imposed on the frequency range $\Omega_{f_{\text{FIB}}}$ and the angle range $\Omega_{\theta_{\text{FIB}}}$. Similar to the concept of spatial variation [6], $f_{\text{re}} \in \Omega_{f_{\text{FIB}}}$ is chosen as the reference frequency point and the spatial variation should be bounded,

$$\sum_{f_j \in \Omega_{f_{\text{FIB}}} - f_{\text{re}}} \sum_{\theta_l \in \Omega_{\theta_{\text{FIB}}}} |B(f_j, \theta_l) - B(f_{\text{re}}, \theta_l)| \leq \varepsilon_{\text{sv}} \quad (11)$$

where ε_{sv} is the threshold for spatial variation to keep the frequency invariant property.

The general optimization issue for wideband beamforming by combining (8) (9) (10) (11) can be presented as,

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize} \sum_{f_j \in \Omega_f} |P(f_j, \theta_{l_0}) - B(f_j, \theta_{l_0})|^2 \\ &\text{subject to} \\ &\sum_{\theta_l \in \Omega_\theta - \theta_{l_0}} |B(f_j, \theta_l)| \leq \varepsilon_{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j) \\ &f_j \in \Omega_f \\ &|B(f_j, \theta_l)| \leq \varepsilon_{\text{nulling}}(f_j, \theta_l) \\ &f_j \in \Omega_{f_{\text{nulling}}} \\ &\theta_l \in \Omega_{\theta_{\text{nulling}}} \\ &\sum_{f_j \in \Omega_{f_{\text{FIB}}} - f_{\text{re}}} \sum_{\theta_l \in \Omega_{\theta_{\text{FIB}}}} |B(f_j, \theta_l) - B(f_{\text{re}}, \theta_l)| \leq \varepsilon_{\text{sv}} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

III. ROBUST WIDEBAND BEAMFORMING

However, due to the limitation of sounding and calibration procedure, channel impulse responses or channel transfer functions of RF chains can not be obtained exactly. The uncertainty will be introduced for wideband beamforming. It is assumed in this paper that the uncertainty is imposed on the discrete channel transfer function h_{m,θ_l,f_j} and the uncertainty is bounded by the known value,

$$h_{m,\theta_l,f_j} = h_{m,\theta_l,f_j}^0 + \Delta h_{m,\theta_l,f_j} \quad (13)$$

and

$$|\Delta h_{m,\theta_l,f_j}| \leq \mu_{m,\theta_l,f_j} \quad (14)$$

where h_{m,θ_l,f_j}^0 is the nominal value of channel transfer function, $\Delta h_{m,\theta_l,f_j}$ is the corresponding uncertainty and μ_{m,θ_l,f_j} is the bounded value for uncertainty.

From Eqn. (7) and Eqn. (13),

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l))_{1,i} &= (h_{m,\theta_l,f_j}^0 + \Delta h_{m,\theta_l,f_j}) \exp\{-\sqrt{-1}n2\pi f_j T_s\} \\ &= (\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l))_{1,i} + (\Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l))_{1,i} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where

$$(\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l))_{1,i} = h_{m,\theta_l,f_j}^0 \exp\{-\sqrt{-1}n2\pi f_j T_s\} \quad (16)$$

and

$$(\Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l))_{1,i} = \Delta h_{m,\theta_l,f_j} \exp\{-\sqrt{-1}n2\pi f_j T_s\} \quad (17)$$

From Eqn. (14) and Eqn. (17),

$$\begin{aligned} |(\Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l))_{1,i}| &= |\Delta h_{m,\theta_l,f_j} \exp\{-\sqrt{-1}n2\pi f_j T_s\}| \\ &= |\Delta h_{m,\theta_l,f_j}| |\exp\{-\sqrt{-1}n2\pi f_j T_s\}| \\ &\leq \mu_{m,\theta_l,f_j} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Define,

$$\mathbf{p} = \begin{bmatrix} P(f_1, \theta_{l_0}) \\ P(f_2, \theta_{l_0}) \\ \vdots \\ P(f_{J+1}, \theta_{l_0}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

and

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{s}(f_1, \theta_{l_0}) \\ \mathbf{s}(f_2, \theta_{l_0}) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{s}(f_{J+1}, \theta_{l_0}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

From Eqn. (2), the objective (8) can be equivalently cast as least square,

$$\text{minimize } \|\mathbf{S}\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{p}\|_2 \quad (21)$$

Further,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}\{\mathbf{S}\} & -\text{Im}\{\mathbf{S}\} \\ \text{Im}\{\mathbf{S}\} & \text{Re}\{\mathbf{S}\} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{w}} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}\{\mathbf{w}\} \\ \text{Im}\{\mathbf{w}\} \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathbf{p}} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}\{\mathbf{p}\} \\ \text{Im}\{\mathbf{p}\} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

where $\text{Re}\{\bullet\}$ returns the real part of complex value and $\text{Im}\{\bullet\}$ returns the imagery part of complex value. Thus the objective (21) can be rewritten as,

$$\text{minimize } \|\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{w}} - \tilde{\mathbf{p}}\|_2 \quad (25)$$

The uncertainty from h_{m,θ_l,f_j} is embedded in $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}^0 + \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{S}} \quad (26)$$

and

$$\|\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{S}}\|_F \leq \sqrt{\sum_{f_j \in \Omega_f} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} 2N \mu_{m,\theta_{l_0},f_j}^2} \quad (27)$$

where the right hand side of inequality (27) is defined as ρ .

Thus the worst case residual for the objective (25) is given by [7],

$$\text{minimize } \|\tilde{\mathbf{S}}^0 \tilde{\mathbf{w}} - \tilde{\mathbf{p}}\|_2 + \rho \sqrt{\|\tilde{\mathbf{w}}\|_2^2 + 1} \quad (28)$$

From Eqn. (2) and based on the triangle inequality and Cauchy-Schwarz inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} |B(f_j, \theta_l)| &= |\mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| \\ &= |\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w} + \Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| \\ &\leq |\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| + |\Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| \\ &\leq |\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| + \|\Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l)\|_2 \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \\ &\leq |\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| + \sqrt{\sum_{m=0}^{M-1} N \mu_{m,\theta_l,f_j}^2} \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Define,

$$\rho_{\theta_l,f_j} = \sqrt{\sum_{m=0}^{M-1} N \mu_{m,\theta_l,f_j}^2} \quad (30)$$

thus the worst case of $|B(f_j, \theta_l)|$ is defined as $B_{\text{worstcase}}^{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j, \theta_l)$ which is equal to,

$$|\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| + \rho_{\theta_l,f_j} \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \quad (31)$$

The constraint (9) with the consideration of worst case is rewritten as,

$$\sum_{\substack{\theta_l \in \Omega_{\theta} - \theta_{l_0} \\ f_j \in \Omega_f}} B_{\text{worstcase}}^{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j, \theta_l) \leq \varepsilon_{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j) \quad (32)$$

Similarly the constraint (10) with the consideration of worst case is rewritten as,

$$|\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| + \rho_{\theta_l,f_j} \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \leq \varepsilon_{\text{nulling}}(f_j, \theta_l) \quad (33)$$

For the frequency invariant property,

$$\begin{aligned} |B(f_j, \theta_l) - B(f_{\text{re}}, \theta_l)| &= |\mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{s}(f_{\text{re}}, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| \\ &= |(\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) - \mathbf{s}^0(f_{\text{re}}, \theta_l)) \mathbf{w} + (\Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l) - \Delta \mathbf{s}(f_{\text{re}}, \theta_l)) \mathbf{w}| \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Define,

$$\delta(\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l)) = \mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) - \mathbf{s}^0(f_{\text{re}}, \theta_l) \quad (35)$$

and

$$\delta(\Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l)) = \Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l) - \Delta \mathbf{s}(f_{re}, \theta_l) \quad (36)$$

thus

$$\|\delta(\Delta \mathbf{s}(f_j, \theta_l))\|_2 \leq \sqrt{\sum_{m=0}^{M-1} N \mu_{m, \theta_l, f_j}^2 + \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} N \mu_{m, \theta_l, f_{re}}^2} \quad (37)$$

where the right hand side of inequality (37) is defined as $\rho_{\theta_l, f_j, f_{re}}$.

The worse case of $|B(f_j, \theta_l) - B(f_{re}, \theta_l)|$ is defined as $B_{\text{worstcase}}^{\text{sv}}(f_j, f_{re}, \theta_l)$ which is equal to,

$$|\delta(\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l)) \mathbf{w}| + \rho_{\theta_l, f_j, f_{re}} \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \quad (38)$$

The constraint (11) with the consideration of worst case is rewritten as,

$$\sum_{f_j \in \Omega_{f_{\text{FIB}}} - f_{re}} \sum_{\theta_l \in \Omega_{\theta_{\text{FIB}}}} B_{\text{worstcase}}^{\text{sv}}(f_j, f_{re}, \theta_l) \leq \varepsilon_{\text{sv}} \quad (39)$$

The general optimization issue for robust wideband beamforming by combining (28) (32) (33) (39) can be presented as,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} \quad \left\| \tilde{\mathbf{S}} \tilde{\mathbf{w}} - \tilde{\mathbf{p}} \right\|_2 + \rho \sqrt{\|\tilde{\mathbf{w}}\|_2^2 + 1} \\ & \text{subject to} \\ & \sum_{\theta_l \in \Omega_{\theta} - \theta_{l_0}} B_{\text{worstcase}}^{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j, \theta_l) \leq \varepsilon_{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j) \\ & f_j \in \Omega_f \\ & |\mathbf{s}^0(f_j, \theta_l) \mathbf{w}| + \rho_{\theta_l, f_j} \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \leq \varepsilon_{\text{nulling}}(f_j, \theta_l) \\ & f_j \in \Omega_{f_{\text{nulling}}} \\ & \theta_l \in \Omega_{\theta_{\text{nulling}}} \\ & \sum_{f_j \in \Omega_{f_{\text{FIB}}} - f_{re}} \sum_{\theta_l \in \Omega_{\theta_{\text{FIB}}}} B_{\text{worstcase}}^{\text{sv}}(f_j, f_{re}, \theta_l) \leq \varepsilon_{\text{sv}} \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

The relationship between $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}$ and \mathbf{w} is shown in Eqn. (23). CVX (Matlab Software for Disciplined Convex Programming) [8] [9] is used to get the optimal solution $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}^*$. Then the optimal solution \mathbf{w}^* for the 2-dimensional filter bank can be obtained.

IV. PERFORMANCE

The performance of robust wideband beamforming will be verified by the data from TELA Testbed. M is equal to 16. d is equal to $0.01143m$. f_c is equal to 14250MHz . B is equal to 500MHz . T_s is equal to 0.75ns , which means the sample rate of ADC is 1.333GHz .

Assume μ_{m, θ_l, f_j} is equal to 0.001. $\Delta h_{m, \theta_l, f_j}$ follows the uniform distribution. N is equal to 60. L is equal to 60, which means the angle resolution is 3° . J is equal to 20, which means the frequency resolution is 25MHz . θ_{l_0} is equal to 90° . The desired main beam pattern $P(f_j, \theta_l) = 1$. $\varepsilon_{\text{sidelobe}}(f_j)$ is equal to 3. $\Omega_{f_{\text{nulling}}} = \{f_{11}, f_{12}, \dots, f_{15}\}$, $\Omega_{\theta_{\text{nulling}}} = \{150^\circ\}$ and $\varepsilon_{\text{nulling}}(f_j, \theta_l)$ are all set to be $10^{-1.5}$. $\Omega_{f_{\text{FIB}}} = \Omega_f$, $f_{re} = f_{J+1}$, $\Omega_{\theta_{\text{FIB}}} = \{75^\circ, 78^\circ, 81^\circ, 84^\circ, 87^\circ, 93^\circ, 96^\circ, 99^\circ, 102^\circ, 105^\circ\}$ and ε_{sv} is set to be 2.5. Thus ρ is equal to 0.2008. ρ_{f_j, θ_l} is equal to 0.031. $\rho_{\theta_l, f_j, f_{re}}$ is equal to 0.0438. Fig. 1 shows the designed

Fig. 1. Designed wideband beam pattern with uncertain discrete channel transfer function.

wideband beam pattern with uncertain discrete channel transfer function.

Taking the non-robust wideband beamforming, which means μ_{m, θ_l, f_j} is equal to 0, as comparison. By 1000 independent realizations of discrete channel transfer function, for robust wideband beamforming, the mean of $\left\| \tilde{\mathbf{S}} \tilde{\mathbf{w}} - \tilde{\mathbf{p}} \right\|_2$ is 0.5524

and the variance of $\left\| \tilde{\mathbf{S}} \tilde{\mathbf{w}} - \tilde{\mathbf{p}} \right\|_2$ is round $7.5 * 10^{-9}$; for non-robust wideband beamforming, the corresponding mean is 0.0505 and the variance is round $3.0 * 10^{-5}$. Thus robust wideband beamforming can give a more stable solution than its non-robust counterpart to combat uncertainty. However the prices of this advantage are (1) the size of the optimization issue is increased for robust wideband beamforming; (2) the optimal objective value for robust wideband beamforming becomes larger mainly because the constraints are tighter with the consideration of the worst case situation. The other advantage of robust wideband beamforming is that all the constraints are perfectly met as long as the uncertainty is bounded. While for non-robust wideband beamforming, some of the constraints will be violated due to the introduction of uncertainty. Meanwhile, based on the formulation of robust wideband beamforming, the total energy of coefficients for the 2-dimensional filter bank $\|\tilde{\mathbf{w}}\|_2^2$ is constrained implicitly, which can reduce the total noise power after the 2-dimensional filter bank.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper studies robust wideband beamforming. The uncertainty is imposed on the discrete channel transfer function of RF chain and the uncertainty is assumed to be bounded by the known value. Robust optimization is exploited and worst case performance can be guaranteed. However, robust optimization with the consideration of worst case situation is too conservative sometimes. Thus more information about uncertainty should be explored in the future and robust wideband beamforming should be reformulated with loose constraints. In

this way, the overall performance of wideband beamforming can be improved.

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